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Called to Be a Missionary of God's Mercy

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A fervent Catholic friend of mine, Sally, has been suffering from a variety of illnesses for years. She was hoping to have a child with her husband but that was not possible due to her poor health. At one point she was struggling with disappointment and doubts in God. As a survivor of a somewhat serious health threat, I encouraged her to consider her mission might not be in maternity. She could be invited by God to testify for God's merciful providence through her ill health. This, of course, does not mean that God is responsible for her ill health. Rather, how much God has supported her and was with her through all her illnesses. How her life is richer with meanings because of all the challenges. With that interior understanding, she became free to testify for God's merciful providence and the meaning of her suffering.

The First Week of the Spiritual Exercises of St. Ignatius puts the retreatants in contemplation on their own sinfulness. The main objective is to help them experience how much God has loved them, though serious sinners they are. Being enflamed with the love of God, they are set free to respond to God's invitation ever so generously, bringing reconciliation and the joy of the Gospel to the world. Jesuits see themselves as sinners, yet called to be companions of Jesus as Ignatius and his first

companions did. Being called to be a companion of our Lord is a grace not deserved by anyone, who are sinners to begin with, but a pure loving invitation of God.

A definition of mercy is the feeling that motivates compassion. And compassion is about feeling for the suffering of others and a desire to do something to alleviate their pain.

As fellow Christians, we are all called to be followers and companions of Christ. We are sinners, yet loved! Once you and I have this affective understanding of what is meant by 'sinner yet loved,' who am I to judge the other sinners then? Who am I to

distinguish myself from them, to make myself better or holier than them? What right do I have to despise or condemn anyone out right and mercilessly? It is so tempting to make our religion into a 'right or wrong' differentiating machine, or to see reality in duality. Is this what God or Christianity about? Our experience of mercy moves us to see God as God is. Mercy defines who we are as Christians, children of God who is Love. God, who is dynamic, ever involving and laboring for us. Hence, Christian faith is essentially the merciful love of God concretely manifested in the incarnation and paschal mystery of the Son of God.

How to understand mercy? Is it the same as compassion? A definition of mercy is the feeling that motivates compassion. And compassion is about feeling for the suffering of others and a desire to do something to alleviate their pain. One cannot, therefore, feeling bad for someone but staying put in one's affective state. "*So also faith of itself, if it does not have works, is dead.*" (James 2:17) Faith, mercy and compassion are intertwined. Faith without mercy is just a form without real content. Mercy without compassion is just self-serving

sympathetic feeling. Action is the end result of the faith-mercy-compassion composite. And this action is mission.

“[Mercy] was the resumption of a journey of encountering people where they live: in their cities and homes, in their workplaces. Wherever there are people, the Church is called to reach out to them and to bring the joy of the Gospel.”

Many Christians are of the opinion that ‘mission’ is a grand action, going to somewhere far away to evangelize. Hence, we have missionary. But mission really does not have to be so narrowly defined. The original meaning of ‘mission’ or ‘*missionem*’ (*missio*) is ‘to be sent.’ Pope

Francis said in his homily for the inauguration of the Extraordinary Jubilee Year of Mercy, “[*it*] was the resumption of a journey of encountering people where they live: in their cities and homes, in their workplaces. Wherever there are people, the Church is called to reach out to them and to bring the joy of the Gospel.” The Church is not just the institutional or hierarchical Church but also the People of God, i.e., you and me. Pope Francis was referring to a Church impelled by the Holy Spirit “*to emerge from the shoals which for years had kept her self-enclosed so as to set out once again, with enthusiasm, on her missionary journey.*” Yes it is once again, you and me.

If my friend Sally refused to see her ill-health as a form of preparation for herself to become missionary of God’s love, but ruminated in her self-pitying and resentful state instead, she would not be a person so filled with life and joy as she is now. Her energetic and joyful presence radiates hope to the suffering ones as she encounters them.

Compassion is not, necessarily, removing the pain and suffering for others. Rather, it is about being with others, giving them hope that God has not left them to face their own battle. It is

also about helping them create some positive meaning for their suffering. But I need to first allow God to touch my inner wounds with God's merciful gaze. I do not need to deny or repress my pain but acknowledge it with an audacious faith in this merciful and compassionate God. Moreover, I do not need

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to be compassionate out of duty, Christian guilt or intellectual persuasion either. I want to reach out to people with mercy because I myself have experienced the compassion of God in my umpteen weaknesses and failings. Since God

accepts me as I am, always and unconditionally, who am I to condemn others, including my annoying opponents or enjoy seeing them in their sufferings?

This is not to say that we have no need to differentiate between good and evil; it is essential for living morally. However, encouraged by Pope Francis, I am working on incorporating mercy and compassion fundamentals of my lifestyle, but not without emotional and spiritual struggles. I pray that through my mission of mercy, others will experience the compassion of God in their misery, and joy can once again be a sustaining reality in their lives.